

Research and Innovation Action

CESSDA Strengthening and Widening

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<p>Abstract: This report provides information about the 2nd SaW project workshop aiming at the current members and Service Providers within the CESSDA consortium on “Trust and Technical Aspects within the CESSDA infrastructure” held in Zagreb, Croatia on March 1st and 2nd, 2017. The aim of the workshop was to disseminate progress and gather new input on DSA certification among CESSDA Service Providers, as well as to inform about the work in the development package (WP4), with specific emphasis on Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) needed for CESSDA research infrastructure in general.</p> <p>The information in this document reflects only the author’s views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided “as is” without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.</p>	

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on the process of organising and the outcomes of the second event organised within the CESSDA-SaW project. Hosted by the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences (Sveučiliste u Zagrebu Filozofski Fakultet - FFZG), the “Trust and Technical Aspects within the CESSDA infrastructure” event took place in Zagreb, Croatia on the 1st and 2nd of March, 2017. The whole event was planned and realised as combination of several workshops aiming at senior staff members of current and aspiring Service Providers. The topics of workshops were the following: training on how to achieve a Data Seal of Approval (DSA), as required by the CESSDA Annex 2 Obligations; the Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) within CESSDA; the sustainability and funding models for support services; and the preservation policy guidelines for research data services. The event targeted policy/decision making level of staff members (for DSA and sustainability models), and technical staff members (for AAI).

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
ADP	Arhiv druzboslovnih podatkov, Univerza v Ljubljani
ADS	Polish Social Data Archive
AUSSDA	Austrian Social Science Data Archive
CESSDA AS	Consortium of European Social Sciences Data Archives, main office
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (Progedo)
CSDA	Czech Social Science Data Archive
DANS-KNAW	Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen
DAASI	DASSI International GmbH
DDA	Danish National Archive - Danish Data Archive
DoA	Description of Action
DSA	Data Seal of Approval
EKKE	Ethniko Kentro Koinonikon Erevnon
ESSDA	Estonian Social Science Data Archive
FFZG	Sveuciliste u Zagrebu Filozofski Fakultet
FORS	Swiss Foundation for Research in the Social Sciences
FSD	Finnish Social Science Data Archive
GESIS	GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
GA	Grant Agreement
ICS-ULISBOA	Instituto De Ciências Sociais Da Universidade De Lisboa
IEN	Institut Ekonomskih Nauka
NSD	Norsk samfunnsvitenskapelig datatjeneste AS
UCD ISSDA	University College Dublin, Irish Social Science Data Archive
RODA	Asociatia Arhiva Română de Date Sociale
SOHDA	Université Catholique de Louvain, SSH Data Archive
SP	Service Provider
SRCE	University of Zagreb Computing Centre
SU SAV	Sociologický ústav Slovenskej akadémie vied
TARKI	TARKI ALAPITVANY (TARKI Foundation)
UGOT- SND	University of Gothenburg - Swedish National Data Service
UKDA	United Kingdom Data Archive
UNIData	Università degli studi di Milano-Bicocca Data Archive

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1. INTRODUCTION

The aim of the task 2.3, as defined by the Description of Action (DoA) of the Grant Agreement (GA), is to communicate the core messages of the project in the way best suited to the target audiences identified at the start of the project. It also aims to inform the progress of tasks directly targeted at strengthening of the current consortium members and support of the potential Service Providers during the project duration.

In order to achieve that, organisation of four workshops was planned in the course of the project; two aimed at strengthening the network through knowledge exchange, and two geared towards widening the network via networking activities with national ministries, Research Councils, and the Social Sciences research community.

The first stakeholder workshop aimed at strengthening the current network was organised in The Hague in June 2016 and provided training on DSA certification, identifying demand and networking. The second strengthening workshop of CESSDA-SaW entitled “Trust and Technical Aspects within the CESSDA infrastructure” took place on 1-2 March 2017 in Zagreb, Croatia.

This report informs about the organisational process behind the latter event in terms of target audience (profile, show-up rate, level of staff, number of attendees, gender balance, etc.), outreach (member countries and potential member countries coverage, person per institution, etc.) and its outputs by briefly describing the aim and topics presented through plenary speeches and parallel sessions. More in-depth analysis of specific sessions of this event, summed up into a separate workshop on AAI, will be described in deliverable 4.2.

The event on “Trust and Technical Aspects within the CESSDA infrastructure” was initially planned to be held in M18 (January 2017). Given that most planning and on-site organisation had to be done in December 2016 in the middle of the holiday season, with target audience mostly absent on winter vacation until mid-January, the workshop was postponed until M20 (March 2017) and decided to be held in one of the potential member countries - Croatia.

This deliverable has been scheduled for submission in the end of April 2017. Given the number of parallel events' organisation, and ongoing preparations for the CESSDA ERIC launch, review process has suffered a lot of delays. However, this is the last of 2 planned strengthening events, and D2.5 and related reports and their results will be further incorporated in usual business and operations of CESSDA and CESSDA ERIC. Therefore, quality was preferred over timely delivery.

2. BACKGROUND OF DISSEMINATION EVENTS IN THE SAW PROJECT

Task 2.3 manages the organisation of workshops mentioned in different sections of the Work Packages 2, 3 and 4. Given both the number of planned events and organisational issues identified after the project beginning, the overall number of workshops was prioritised, merged and limited wherever possible. After rescheduling done during the 2nd consortium meeting in Bergen in February 2016, 5 events were identified as priority. However, strategic decision to postpone the 1st Collaborative workshop due to political situations in several potential member countries from M15 to M22, incurred the loss of time slot for the 2nd Collaborative workshop, and required another re-scheduling of events. The new schedule put the events in the following months: M11, M20, M22 and M27. Previously planned, but smaller, separate events were included as sessions covering important topics that needed to be addressed in face-to-face meetings.

1.1. DISTRIBUTION OF EVENTS

Rescheduled distribution of events was intended to bring higher cost efficiency, and more effectiveness in achieving continuity of work. Events were organised around demands of different tasks, as well as target audiences (Table 1 below). The main principle for grouping dissemination activities into events was to have 2 workshops aiming at strengthening of the current consortium, and 2 workshops aiming at widening of the consortium by outreach towards the potential member countries and/or potential Service Providers. Instead of 2 widening workshops, the final distribution of events includes one widening workshop and the final high-level event aiming at further widening of the CESSDA network of potential member countries and SPs.

Table 1: Final distribution of events

1. Workshop on Archives 1st workshop on DSA guidelines	T2.3 Stakeholder workshop report 1+T4.4 Bring the demand information together+T4.3 Guidelines for CESSDA members on DSA certification + T4.6 Cost-benefit analysis
2. 1st Collaborative Workshop on establishing partnerships	T2.3 Stakeholder workshop report 2+T4.5 1st Collaborative workshop on Establishing partnerships between CESSDA & SPs+ T4.6 Cost-benefit analysis+T3.2 Audit of current status of data archives in all ERA countries+T3.4 Strengthening and widening through expanding data perimeter)
3. Integration workshop 2nd workshop on DSA guidelines	T2.3 Stakeholder workshop report 3+T4.3 Trust workshop+T4.2 Development of the necessary administrative, technical, and methodological support needed to establish and develop trustworthy data archives+T4.4 Support for Establishing the necessary conditions for creating new or reinforcing existing social science data services
4. Final Dissemination event high visibility and high impact event	Bringing together stakeholders of social sciences data infrastructures (including national ministries/research councils in potential member countries) to demonstrate seamless data archive service + special focus on the user experience of searching for data, focusing on widened CESSDA network

Workshops 1 and 3 were planned to strengthen and support administrative, methodological and technical practices of CESSDA Service Providers and archives in aspiring member countries. They should target staff of the Service Providers and potential SPs.

The second group of workshops (2 and 4) was intended to widen the perimeter of the consortium by meeting with aspiring member countries' representatives. These workshops should showcase the best practices of large SPs, highlight models for sustainability, and promote archiving services and funding opportunities. They should aim at the high-level officials from ministries, research councils, and/or funding agencies in the non-member countries, as well as at the potential service providers and research community.

The second workshop, "Collaborative workshop on establishing partnerships between CESSDA and potential Service Providers", was initially planned to be held in Budapest, Hungary in October 2016 (M15). It was cancelled due to the poor registrations rates. The main reason behind cancellation of this workshop was the high level of political uncertainty in several potential member countries such as Croatia, Serbia or Romania in the last quarter of 2016. Political events in those and other target countries (regular and/or repeated elections, protests, changes within governments officials, etc.) led to a very low number of high-level registrants for the event. Given the importance of this event for the widening activities of CESSDA, postponing was the only option. This workshop was postponed for 7 months; it will be held in Lisbon, Portugal on 3-4 May 2017, and hosted by ICS ULisboa, beneficiary in the SaW project and potential CESSDA SP.

However, postponing of the 2nd workshop (or 1st Collaborative workshop on establishing partnerships between CESSDA and potential Service Providers) to M22 (May 2017) changed the order of the planned events, leaving the consortium with no time for the 2nd Collaborative workshop on establishing partnerships between CESSDA and potential Service Providers (originally planned in M20) to be held before the project end. New layout of the planned events is presented in Picture 1. Therefore, current plan includes 3 workshops and the final dissemination conference that will replace the 2nd Collaborative workshop on widening and provide several themed sessions about CESSDA and partnerships with non-member countries and archives.

Picture 1: Workshops and Final Event Planning

3. 2ND TRAINING WORKSHOP ON TRUST, AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS WITHIN THE CESSDA INFRASTRUCTURE

3.1. AIM OF THE WORKSHOP

As the first strengthening workshop in Den Haag, the second one also focused on knowledge exchange between the current CESSDA Service Providers and social science data archives from aspiring countries. The main broad areas of interest covered in this workshop (or set of workshops) were the following: development of necessary administrative, technical, and methodological support needed to establish and develop trustworthy data archives, support of necessary conditions for creating new or reinforcing existing social science data services, and update on the ongoing technical activities in CESSDA.

This was achieved by offering further training on Trust and guidelines how to achieve a Data Seal of Approval (as required by the CESSDA Statutes in the Annex 2 Obligations), by providing insight into needed developments in order to establish a confederated AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure) service within CESSDA, by discussing possible funding models, and preservation policy guidelines for research data services. Additionally, an update on Technical Roadmap was offered in the end, as underlying process/framework for all technical activities within CESSDA.

Picture 2: Online Registration form - Snapshot

The image shows a snapshot of an online registration form. At the top, the logos for 'cessda' and 'saw' are displayed. Below the logos, the title of the workshop is '3rd Training Workshop on Widening the European infrastructure of social science data archives', followed by the dates '1 & 2 March 2017, Zagreb, Croatia'. A note states: 'Please note that the information you will provide will not be disclosed.' A red asterisk indicates required fields. A link is provided: 'Check the CESSDA-SaW webpage for information about the workshop here: <http://cessdasaw.eu/category/workshop/>'. The form contains several input fields: 'Your first name *', 'Your last name *', 'Your e-mail address *', and 'Name of your organisation *'. Below these is a section for 'Indicate your role in your institution *' with a list of roles: 'Management of the Service Provider', 'Policy adviser', 'Involved in DSA certification', 'Technical staff', 'Data management', 'Domain expert', and 'Other:'. Each role has a corresponding checkbox.

Picture 3: CESSDA SaW Website - Workshop Webpage - Snapshot

WS 2 – Workshop – Zagreb, HR – 01-02/03/2017

Second Training workshop on Trust and Technical Aspects within the CESSDA infrastructure

Date: Wed 01 March 2017 09:00 – Thu 02 March 2017 15:00

PLEASE FOLLOW THE LINK TO REGISTER : [Click Here!](#)

DEADLINE FOR HOTEL DISCOUNT : 7th February 2017
DEADLINE FOR REGISTRATION : 20th February 2017

The CESSDA SaW project has successfully accomplished the first year of its duration and all obligations in that period. We are now well underway with activities in the second year.

Part of the dissemination activities is the organization of three workshops; two for the strengthening of the network through knowledge exchange, one for widening the network via networking activities with national ministries, Research Councils, and the Social Sciences research community.

We would like to invite staff members of your Service Provider to the second CESSDA SaW workshop aiming at strengthening of the network through knowledge exchange.

The topics of the workshop will be:

- **Trust: training on how to achieve a Data Seal of Approval (as required by the CESSDA Annex 2 Obligations),**
- **Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) within CESSDA,**
- **Sustainability and funding models for support services,**

WorkShop 2

“Widening the European infrastructure of social science data archives”

01-02 / 03 / 2017

WS2 - Registration

WS2 - Programme

WS2 - Location

WS2 - How to get there

WS 1 - CONTACT INFO

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Disclaimer:

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3.2. WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

3.2.1. TARGET AUDIENCE

WS2 targeted individuals from CESSDA SaW beneficiaries and linked third parties (CESSDA SPs) and other aspiring archives, who have an overview of the technical needs of their institution and can follow through on implementing DSA certification. The target audience of this WS was therefore mainly composed of senior staff members. Anticipating the level of coverage and potential attendees as the previous time, all European Research Area countries (ERA) were considered. However, not all ERA could be covered due to lack of appropriate contacts in some of the countries.

Out of 37 identified countries, participants from 26 countries attended the workshop: Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia (FYRM), Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom.

Picture 4: Map of Invited Countries

As stated in Table 2 below, 30 institutions were represented in the workshop, all sending between one and two representatives. Participation was rather strong since almost all invited institutions took part, ensuring information shared during the numerous sessions was spread amongst members of the consortium and beyond.

Table 2: Participants per Institution

Institution	Participants			
	1	2	3	4
DANS				
ADP				
CESSDA AS				
CNRS (Progedo)				
FFZG				
SRCE				
UKDS				
FSD				
AuSSDA				
DDA				
CSDA				
EKKE				
GESIS				
FORS				
ICS-ULisboa/APIs				
IEN				
Institute for sociological, political and juridical research - Macedonia				
ADS				
NSD				
UniData - Bicocca Data Archive				
SND				
SOHDA				
TARKI				
ESSDA				
UCD ISSDA				
Research Center of the Latvian Academy of Culture				
RODA				
DAASI				
SU SAV				
Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research, Zagreb				

In total, 62 participants attended the workshop. The attendees represented the widened CESSDA SaW network consisting of CESSDA Service providers' staff, and representatives of CESSDA SaW project beneficiaries representing aspiring CESSDA social science data archives and services. High participation rate provides insight into networking efforts beyond actual membership, which is one of the goals all workshops, regardless of their strengthening or widening nature.

3.2.2. STAFF ATTENDING PER ROLE AND GENDER BALANCE

The main target audiences of WS2 were both technical staff and higher positioned management representatives with decision making power. Figure below enables comparison of attendees' profiles enrolled to attend the event. Attendees were asked in the registration form to specify the type of position they hold in their institutions.

The variety of positions represented amongst attendees is reflected in the Figure 1 below. Relative variations amongst attendees can be noticed regarding the positions they hold within their institutions, showing that technical staff category was the least represented category. Data experts were those who were the most represented within the assembly, followed by people occupying strategic, business or data management positions in a SP.

Figure 1: Variety of positions represented amongst attendees

The attendance figures (as shown in Figure 2 below) are relative depending on the size of particular archives. Attendees were able to declare several positions, so the occupation of different roles can affect the final results up to some extent. Namely, some archives/SPs are quite small with limited staff, therefore the same person may occupy several positions.

Since the WS2 was not exclusively aiming at technical staff, it is not surprising to see different profiles attending the event.

Figure 2: Number of participants for each category

One of the European Commission regulations emphasises the need to respect gender balance when organising activities within EU projects, and that is demonstrated in the Figure 3 below. Both men and women are fairly represented with a slight head start for men on service manager positions. However, within specific fields there is a significant lack of a balanced gender representation (i.e. data managers are mostly women, and technical specialists are mostly men); this could indicate the tendency of staff recruitments within the field, and therefore should be addressed in future policy approach on institutional level.

Figure 3: Attendee gender balance per role

4. TOPICS

The whole event was executing as a series of independent workshops, and each evolved around a common topic. The following topics were supported in the [programme](#):

- Trust: training on how to achieve a Data Seal of Approval (as required by the CESSDA Annex 2 Obligations);
- Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) within CESSDA;
- Sustainability and funding models for support services;
- Preservation policy guidelines for research data services.

Plenary sessions served as introductions into more detailed parallel sessions. They covered a broad range of topics such as general updates about the recent developments with the CESSDA infrastructure, and administrative updates about the SaW project itself by the Coordinator. Introduction and general overview of Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), was provided by external expert Peter Gietz, CEO of DAASI International GmbH. Finally, preservation policy guidelines for research data services, part of Task 4.2, were presented by the task leader.

Two main threads of parallel sessions were held throughout both days: one on Trust support activities (DSA certification progress and efforts), and the other on AAI future developments within CESSDA. Additional parallel sessions were held on strengthening the CESSDA SP community through sustainable support services, and on Dataverse and how it can be used to strengthen and develop new research services.

Special addition to the programme was the last session on CESSDA Technical Roadmap - the strategic outlook presented by the CESSDA Technical Working group leader John Shepherdson (UKDA).

4.1. SUMMARIES OF SESSIONS

1. Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI)

The introductory session presented the basic concepts of Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), and the advantages of using AAI solutions. It briefly presented the other European AAI projects, besides AAI federations and inter-federations. Then the session continued with CESSDA's current technical work plans and the role of CESSDA AAI to provide secure access to sensitive data. Big picture of current Service Providers' AAI and a proposed CESSDA AAI was presented.

The following two sessions focused on details of AAI systems and the existing AAI solutions. The sessions present successful projects such as DARIAH and AARC. Maintaining the CESSDA AAI was outlined as an important concern. After implementing the AAI, CESSDA should provide IT service operation procedure and policy for maintaining the infrastructure.

Three significant outcomes of the AAI sessions are as follows:

1. Roughly identifying the most suitable AAI solutions for CESSDA,
2. Extracting the Service Providers' initial requirements and concerns,
3. Learning the concepts of AAI and knowing more about the similar projects.

2. TRUST Sessions

There were three sessions about Trust and the Data Seal of Approval, aiming at the staff of Service Providers involved in the DSA assessment.

In the first session, the Gap Analysis Report was presented. This report is based on the self-assessments sent in by all participants. It was followed by a discussion on all the issues, and “gaps”, emerged in the report. In the second session, the discussion on the gaps continued. Formulation of general lessons and guidance for the CESSDA SP’s concerning DSA certification was offered, in attempt to answer the common questions i.e. How much guidance is needed? Should it be Individually, or collectively? Etc. The third session continued with discussions, but with a focus on the time schedule and the planning of activities for the rest of 2017 (or by the end of the project duration and beyond).

3. Preservation Policy Guidelines for research data services

This session presented the preliminary results from task 4.2, which aims to provide resources and guidelines for the development of service provider policies. The task develops a template that can assist well-established and new/developing data archives to prepare, articulate and upgrade their policy framework.

The session presented the model and framework of the new policy recommendations on different levels: at the organisational level, there is the *Mission Statement* and the *Strategic Plan*; on the implementation level, there is the *Curation Policies* document (including collection policy, preservation policy and access policy) and the *Implementation Plan*. The relationship between these terms is as follows: a Service Provider is assumed to have an overall Mission Statement, part of which will be concerned with preservation. The Strategic Plan states how the mission will be achieved, in general terms with goals and objectives. The Curation policies then declares the range of approaches that the repository will employ to ensure preservation (that is, to implement the Strategic Plan). Finally, the Implementation Plan translates those into services that the repository must carry out. It was noted that this is an abstract documentary model that can result in different documentation generation, with different labels, topics, etc.

4. Dataverse and how it can be used to strengthen and develop new research data services

Within work package 4, a number of Dataverse pilots were based upon partner needs to evaluate both Dataverse as a platform for provision of solutions for user communities, and to establish how, as a community within CESSDA SAW, Service Providers from and outside CESSDA could support each other.

This session consisted of 3 presentations and time was allocated to discuss the key challenges:

- Strengthening the CESSDA SP community through sustainable support services;
- Dataverse: an introduction;
- How Dataverse is being used in the SaW pilots.

5. CESSDA Technical Roadmap

The intention was to disseminate information about CESSDA technical developments (past, present and future) for the period 2015 - 2018, excluding collaborative projects such as SaW, SERISS and BDE. It was also an opportunity to go through the approaches that CESSDA is mandating for Service Providers and other suppliers for the provision of software products intended to form part of the Research Infrastructure.

The presentation was divided into three sections. Section one dealt with the technical roadmap, giving a summary of planned/ongoing/completed work for 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018, followed by more detail for each project or task that year. Section two went into details about the Technical Framework, which is the set of standards that provide guidance for developers of CESSDA software products, plus the infrastructure for developing, testing, accepting and running them. It included a section that explained CESSDA's Product Acceptance Criteria, which are used to ensure software meets the required standards, before being made available to end users. Section three looked at the next level of technical detail, dealing specifically with designing and building 'cloud native' software. It discussed each of Heroku's so called 12 factors (12factor.net) in turn, to show how and why they would be adopted. It concluded with a brief question and answer session.

In summary, the session was aimed at a technical audience, but contained enough to get interested non-technical colleagues up to speed with what products and services are being designed and built for CESSDA's Research Infrastructure, and to what standards.

5. CONCLUSION

This deliverable reported on the process of organising workshops in general, and in more details, it reported on preparation and conduct of WS2. The first section of this report describes the organisational issues as well as the way they were addressed in order to provide insight on the final layout of workshops, and their relation to topics, target audiences and reported outcomes.

D2.5 describes the organisation of the second of the 4 CESSDA SaW events: two workshops were meant to strengthen the network through knowledge exchange between current and aspiring CESSDA Service Providers (SPs), two were aiming at widening the consortium via networking activities that bring together national ministries, Services Providers, Research Councils, and potentially the Social Sciences research community.

As already described, the main intention of WS2 was to train and further support both technical staff and management representatives of CESSDA Service Providers and all SaW partners in obtaining the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) certification, providing needed information and plan actions in developing federated Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) within CESSDA, discussing sustainability and funding models for support services, and finally, developing preservation policy guidelines for research data services. Underlying CESSDA Technical Roadmap was also described and explained as overall framework of technical developments in CESSDA.

The attendance and active participation of all CESSDA SPs in addition to aspiring countries' representatives, demonstrates the functioning of the widened CESSDA network of service providers, and their successful integration into CESSDA plans and activities.

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